

RESEARCH

Open Access

Phenol-driven cometabolic degradation of *cis*-1,2-dichloroethene (cDCE): insights from *Acinetobacter pittii* and *Ectopseudomonas alcaliphila*

Miguel Desmarais^{1,7†}

Abstract

Accumulation of xenobiotic chlorinated ethenes (CEs) at legacy industrial soil and groundwater sites around the world is a pressing environmental and public health issue. Understanding the biochemical pathways through which microorganisms degrade cDCE is key to developing cost-effective, sustainable bioremediation strategies for CE contamination. Two strains, *Acinetobacter pittii* CEP14 and *Ectopseudomonas alcaliphila* JAB1, isolated from contaminated industrial sites, have demonstrated the ability to cometabolically degrade cDCE in the presence of phenol. In this study, we integrate transcriptomics, using differential gene expression analysis to pinpoint genes induced during cDCE co-metabolism, with proteomics to confirm protein-level expression. We use heterologous expression experiments to demonstrate that phenol monooxygenase is responsible for oxidising cDCE in both strains. Furthermore, we show that CEP14 and JAB1 α -subunits share 71.4% identity with each other but only 14.6–26.5% identity with established monooxygenases with known cDCE-oxidising activity, highlighting the diversity of enzymes that may be capable of cometabolic cDCE degradation. Finally, we hypothesise on a two-branch phenol monooxygenase-mediated cDCE degradation pathway in which the chemical degradative intermediates 2,2-dichloroacetaldehyde and cDCE epoxides are formed. This study sheds light on the biochemical mechanisms by which monoaromatic compounds can enhance the biodegradation of cDCE and demonstrates the potential utilisation of strains CEP14 and JAB1 for the biodegradation of cDCE.

Keywords Phenol monooxygenase, Cometabolic degradation, *Cis*-1,2-dichloroethene (cDCE), Chlorinated ethenes, Transcriptomics, Heterologous gene expression

[†]Miguel Desmarais and Serena Fraraccio have contributed equally to this work.

*Correspondence:
Ondrej Uhlik
ondrej.uhlik@vscht.cz

Full list of author information is available at the end of the article

Background

Accumulation of xenobiotic chlorinated ethenes (CEs) at legacy industrial soil and groundwater sites around the world is a pressing environmental and public health challenge [32]. In the 1900s, perchloroethene (PCE) and trichloroethene (TCE), known as the higher CEs (HCEs), were heavily used for industrial applications [12]. Due to improper handling and disposal, HCEs and their biodegradation products, the lower CEs (LCEs) dichloroethene (DCE) and vinyl chloride (VC), have become prevalent soil and groundwater contaminants globally [13].

HCEs are readily biodegraded to LCEs by fermenters, methanogens, and sulphate reducers in subsurface anoxic environments, whereas LCEs are mineralised under oxic conditions by aerobes [13, 22]. Few microorganisms have demonstrated the ability to oxidise DCE and VC, which leads to the accumulation of these toxic byproducts at CE-contaminated sites worldwide [10, 14, 16, 43]. More importantly, the chemical degradative intermediate *c*DCE, a nephro- and neuro-toxic compound, is often found in greater concentration than its *trans* isomer (*t*DCE) in drinking water supplies (groundwater), causing potential health problems in nearby communities [48]. *c*DCE commonly co-occurs with phenolic pollutants at industrial sites (e.g. petrochemical and pulp and paper facilities), where phenol concentrations can reach tens to hundreds of μM [1, 27]. Given that many aerobic bacteria use phenol as a growth substrate, phenol-driven co-metabolism represents a promising route to degrade *c*DCE under mixed-contaminant conditions. However,

the specific enzymes and pathways by which phenol might induce *c*DCE cometabolism remain unknown, limiting the development of effective, environmentally friendly, and economy-driven bioremediation strategies for these co-contaminated environments [7].

Select microbial strains isolated from CE-contaminated sediments, soil, groundwater, and activated sludge have demonstrated the ability to degrade *c*DCE aerobically. These include *Comamonas testosteroni* RF2, *Cupriavidus* sp. CY-1 *Methylosinus trichosporium* OB3b, *Polaromonas* sp. JS666, *Thauera butanivorans* ATCC 43655, *Pseudomonas stutzeri* OX1, and *Xanthobacter* sp. Py2, to name a few [9, 10, 14, 16, 38, 43, 51]. These microbes degrade *c*DCE in a cometabolic manner. The fortuitous oxidation of *c*DCE depends on the biochemical pathway that utilises other, so-called primary substrates. Methane, toluene, phenol, and natural monoaromatic secondary plant metabolites can serve as primary growth substrates, stimulating *c*DCE degradation [9, 11, 17, 36]. In addition, microcosm studies have demonstrated the potential for aerobic cometabolic degradation of *c*DCE using TCE as the primary growth substrate [47]. Recent studies have investigated the biochemical pathways by which the aerobic cometabolic degradation of *c*DCE occurs. A two-branch monooxygenase-mediated degradation pathway has been proposed in which *c*DCE is initially oxidised to the chemical degradative intermediates 2,2-dichloroacetaldehyde (DCA) and *c*DCE epoxide by a monooxygenase (Fig. 1) [10, 17, 19, 33, 36]. These chemical intermediates are transformed to glyoxylate by a series of enzymatic

Fig. 1 Proposed *c*DCE degradation pathway in CEP14 and JAB1, including experimentally confirmed and hypothetical reactions, enzymes and chemical intermediates involved. *GSH* glutathione, *NAD*⁺ nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide, oxidised form, *NAD(P)H* nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (phosphate), reduced

reactions involving aldehyde dehydrogenases, haloacid dehalogenases (HAD), glutathione S-transferases (GST), and epoxide hydrolases, and ultimately fed into the glyoxylate cycle pathway.

Two strains, *Acinetobacter pittii* CEP14 and *Ectopseudomonas alcaliphila* JAB1 (formerly *Pseudomonas alcaliphila* JAB1 as reported by Ridl et al. [36], reclassified by Rudra and Gupta [37]), were isolated, respectively, from groundwater at the Spolchemie chemical factory in Ústí nad Labem and legacy-contaminated soil in Jablonné nad Orlicí—both industrial sites heavily contaminated by chlorinated organic pollutants. They have demonstrated the ability to degrade *c*DCE in the presence of phenol cometabolically; however, the biochemical pathway by which this occurs remains unknown [11, 36]. In this study, we integrate transcriptomics, using differential gene expression analysis to pinpoint genes induced during *c*DCE co-metabolism, with proteomics to confirm protein-level expression. We use heterologous expression experiments to demonstrate that phenol monooxygenase is responsible for oxidising *c*DCE in both strains. Finally, we hypothesise on a two-branch phenol monooxygenase-mediated *c*DCE degradation pathway in which the chemical degradative intermediates 2,2-dichloroacetaldehyde and *c*DCE epoxides are formed.

Methods

Experimental design

The experimental design consisted of four treatments: CEP14 and JAB1 cultures were grown in triplicates in minimal salts medium (MSM: NaNO₃ 2.0 g l⁻¹, K₂HPO₄ 0.5 g l⁻¹, MgSO₄·7H₂O 0.2 g l⁻¹, MnSO₄·5H₂O 0.02 g l⁻¹, FeSO₄·7H₂O 0.02 g l⁻¹, CaCl₂ 0.02 g l⁻¹) with either phenol (15 μmol l⁻¹) or sodium pyruvate (15 μmol l⁻¹) as the primary growth substrate, and with or without *c*DCE (15 μmol l⁻¹) as the secondary substrate (Supplementary Information Table 1; culture conditions: Desmarais et al. [11], Ridl et al. [36]). A sodium azide-inactivated cell culture was included as a negative control. This design aimed to identify changes in gene expression unique to the degradation of *c*DCE, rather than the utilisation of the primary growth substrates.

Functional annotation and comparative genomics

The complete CEP14 and JAB1 genomes, along with their functional annotations, were retrieved from the GenBank (National Institute of Health). Proteomes were generated and sequences were further annotated using the Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG) database and the KofamKOALA web tool for KEGG ortholog assignment [4, 23, 42]. Gene and protein sequence similarity were calculated, and sequences were screened using the National Center for Biotechnology Information

(NCBI) BlastN and BlastP web tools as well as the Nucleotide Collection (nr/nt) and UniProtKB/Swiss-Prot proteins database [6]. Multiple protein sequence alignments were generated using Clustal Omega using the seeded guide trees and HMM profile–profile techniques on the EMBL-EBI web server [39]. Protein functions were inferred using the InterProScan web tool to obtain protein signatures, predict domains, and classify proteins into families [21].

Transcriptomics and differential gene expression analysis

Samples for transcriptomic analyses were taken during the period of maximal *c*DCE depletion, when the expression of catabolic genes involved in *c*DCE degradation is theoretically at its highest (CEP14: after 9 h, JAB1: after 16 h). Bacterial pellets were resuspended in a solution containing RNA Protect Reagent (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany) and treated with lysozyme (1 mg ml⁻¹). Cells were centrifuged and lysed in RLT buffer (Qiagen) containing beta-mercaptoethanol. RNA extractions were performed on RNeasy Mini spin columns following the manufacturer's protocol (Qiagen), including on-column DNase I digestion. Isolated RNA was subjected to quantity and quality controls (Qubit RNA BR Assay and Agilent RNA 6000 Nano Kit, La Jolla, CA, USA) and sent to Genecore EMBL Heidelberg for NextSeq 75 cycles High Output sequencing.

TruSeq sequencing adapters, indexed adapters, over-represented sequences (poly-A and poly-G tails), short reads (< 50 bp), and low-quality reads (Phred score < 20) were removed using Trimmomatic v0.36 [5]. The quality of RNA-sequencing (RNA-seq) data was assessed pre- and post-processing using FastQC v0.11.9, after which ribosomal RNA sequences were removed using SortMeRNA [3, 24].

An indexed transcriptome was constructed for each strain using the genomic transcript coordinates generated by PGAP as a reference (CEP14: GenBank accession no. CP084921.1-CP084924.1, JAB1: GenBank accession no. CP016162.1) [11, 36, 42]. The processed reads were aligned to their respective transcriptome using Salmon, and transcript counts were quantified [35].

Differentially expressed transcripts were detected using the DESeq2 package for R Programming in RStudio [29]. Briefly, transcript counts for triplicates were normalised and averaged. Four DESeq2 designs were used for the detection of differentially expressed genes: (i) “design = ~ group”, (ii) “design = ~ condition”, (iii) “design = ~ treatment”, and (iv) “design = ~ condition + treatment + condition:treatment”. This combination of designs allowed for the calculation of log₂ fold change of transcript counts between (i) all four treatments, (ii) between primary substrates (cell cultures

grown on phenol versus sodium pyruvate), (iii) between secondary substrates (cell cultures amended with *cDCE* or not), and (iv) between phenol-grown cultures amended with *cDCE* and all other treatments. Cultures grown on *cDCE* alone were used as a negative control, as no significant depletion of *cDCE* was observed [11, 36]. To validate our RNA-Seq dataset, we performed several complementary quality control analyses (Supplementary Information Figs. 1–3). First, hierarchical clustering of variance-stabilised gene counts clearly groups biological replicates by treatment and reveals the expected substrate-driven clustering (Supplementary Information Fig. 1). Next, PCA explains 64–70% of the variance on PC1 and confirms tight within-group clustering for CEP14 and more diffuse grouping in JAB1 (Supplementary Information Fig. 2). Finally, MA plots of the DESeq2 “~ condition + treatment + condition:treatment” model demonstrate the distribution of log₂ fold changes and adjusted *p*-values, supporting our cutoffs of log₂ fold change ≥ 1 (i.e. at least a two-fold change), for strongly upregulated genes with an FDR below 5% (adjusted $p < 0.05$) (Supplementary Information Fig. 3). Together, these metrics attest to the reproducibility of our data and justify the thresholds used for differential expression calls. No RT-qPCR validation of the differentially expressed genes was performed because the original RNA preparations were completely used up during library preparation.

Proteomics

Cell pellets were collected from cultures by centrifugation, lyophilised, and subjected to proteomic analyses at the University College Dublin. The lyophilised powder was reconstituted in distilled water and quantified spectrophotometrically by NanoDrop (Thermo Fisher Scientific). Proteins were collected (200 μ g) and purified by acetone precipitation, redispersed and denatured in 8 M urea and 100 mM ammonium bicarbonate containing 10 mM dithiothreitol at 60 °C for 30 min, and alkylated with 55 mM iodoacetamide. Trypsin digestion was performed overnight at 37 °C at a protein-to-trypsin ratio of 1:50. Peptides were cleaned by C18 StageTips (Thermo Fisher Scientific), vacuum dried, resuspended in 2% acetonitrile and 0.5% acetic acid, and run on a high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC)-coupled Q Exactive Orbitrap with a 60 min gradient. Technical triplicates were assayed for each sample. Data analysis was performed with MaxQuant using the MaxLFQ label-free quantification (LFQ) algorithm for comparative studies, resulting in the identification of proteins present in cultures at the time of sampling [44]. The database search was performed using the following parameters to ensure high-confidence peptide and protein identifications: an initial peptide mass tolerance of 20 ppm, a main search

tolerance of 4.5 ppm, a peptide–spectrum match (PSM) false discovery rate (FDR) of 1%, and a protein FDR of 1%. To assess the robustness and reproducibility of the MS data, we generated Pearson correlation plots of label-free quantification (LFQ) peptide intensities across three technical replicates for each biological replicate (Supplementary Information Fig. 4), which yielded correlation coefficients above 0.95. Unsupervised hierarchical clustering (Supplementary Information Fig. 5) further confirmed condition-specific protein expression by grouping related samples into tight clusters. Although most proteins were identified with one to two peptides, a substantial fraction had more than three (Supplementary Information Fig. 6). Finally, the *Q*-values for all identified proteins were below 0.005 (FDR < 0.5%), underscoring the low overall FDR.

Heterologous gene expression

The genes coding for the multi-component phenol monooxygenase in CEP14 and JAB1 were heterologously expressed in *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) as per the methods reported previously [40, 41]. Briefly, the *dmp-KLMNOP* operons found in each strain were amplified by PCR using genomic DNA isolated from CEP14 and JAB1 cultures as a template (primers specified in Supplementary Information Fig. 7). The amplified gene clusters were inserted into the commercial plasmid pQE-31 backbone (Amp^R, Qiagen) using the In-Fusion[®] HD Cloning Kit (Takara Bio). The resulting vectors, pQE-dmpCEP14 and pQE-dmpJAB1 (Supplementary Information Fig. 7; Supplementary Information Fasta file 1), were used individually to transform *E. coli* DH11S, and transformants were selected on LB agar supplemented with 150 mg l⁻¹ ampicillin. Resulting strains were then used for heterologous expression of respective gene clusters following the methodology reported previously [40, 41]. Live and auto-claved *E. coli* DH11S cells containing an empty pQE-31 served as a reference.

Phenol and *cDCE* depletion assays and measurements of degradative intermediates

The capacity of JAB1 and CEP14 to deplete phenol and *cDCE*, as well as that of *E. coli* cells bearing pQE31-dmpCEP14 and pQE31-dmpJAB1, was tested using whole-cell assays as per the methods of Suman et al. [41]. Briefly, JAB1 and CEP14 cells were inoculated in 200 ml of MSM containing phenol (10 mM phenol, starting OD 0.05). Cultures were kept at 28 °C with continuous aeration (130 rpm) until they reached an OD of 0.4–0.5. These cultures and IPTG-induced *E. coli* cultures were washed twice, resuspended in MSM, aliquoted into 10 ml glass vials, and sealed with crimp caps coated with aluminium. For whole-cell

cometabolism assays, CEP14 and JAB1 cultures were amended with 15 $\mu\text{mol l}^{-1}$ phenol and *c*DCE and incubated at 28 °C for 12 h (CEP14) or 20 h (JAB1). In parallel, *E. coli* strains carrying pQE31-dmpCEP14 or pQE31-dmpJAB1 were grown at 28 °C in the presence of 200 $\mu\text{mol l}^{-1}$ phenol and *c*DCE, with samples taken at 4, 22, 42, 46, and 70 h. Catechol measurements were not taken for the CEP14 and JAB1 whole-cell transcriptomic and proteomic assays and were only quantified in our heterologous expression experiments (Supplementary Information Fig. 8). Concentrations of catechol as well as *c*DCE and its hypothetical degradation products, DCA, and 2,2-dichloroacetic acid, were determined by comparison with standards using a DANI Master VH gas chromatograph (GC) equipped with an ECD detector, an Rtx-VMS capillary column (Restek, Edmond, OK, USA), and a Master SHS static headspace auto-sampler as reported previously [31]. Phenol content was measured using the HPLC NexeraXR system with an SPD-M20A UV/VIS diode array detector (Shimadzu, Carlsbad, CA, USA) as described elsewhere [28]. MSM-washed cell suspensions were autoclaved (121 °C, 15 min) and used analogously as live cells to measure the effect of microbial biomass on phenol and *c*DCE degradation. In addition, a solution of *c*DCE in

MSM was incubated in parallel to assess the non-enzymatic (abiotic) depletion of *c*DCE.

Results

Expression and translation of putative genes involved in phenol and catechol degradation

The genomes of CEP14 and JAB1 harbour gene clusters encoding putative enzymes involved in the degradation of phenol (Fig. 2) [11, 36]. In CEP14, these degradative genes are located within two discrete gene clusters that are separated by 728 kbp along the genome (Fig. 2A). They encode a phenol monooxygenase responsible for the oxidation of phenol to catechol (*dmpKLMNOP*) as well as all genes involved in the catechol *ortho*-cleavage (*catABC*) and β -keto adipate (*pcaDFIJ*) pathways that encode enzymes carrying out the degradation of catechol to acetyl CoA and succinate [50]. In JAB1, genes involved in the degradation of phenol are located within one contiguous gene cluster whose structure is identical to that of the *dmp* operon found in *Pseudomonas pseudoalcaligenes* strain C70 and *Pseudomonas* sp. strain CF600 [20]. This operon encodes a phenol monooxygenase (*dmpKLMNOP*) and all genes involved in the catechol *meta*-cleavage pathway (*dmpBCDEFGHI*) that encode enzymes carrying out the degradation of catechol to acetyl CoA

Fig. 2 Genetic structure of genes encoding putative enzymes involved in the complete degradation of phenol in **a** CEP14 and **b** JAB 1 and their respective chemical intermediates (**b**, **c**). These gene clusters include the *dmp* operon (position range 1,861,099–1,866,822) and *cat-pca* operon (position range 2,594,895–2,600,570) in **b**, **c** CEP14 and the *dmp* operon (position range 4,397,470–4,409,584) in **d** JAB1. The organisation of the CEP14 *dmpKLMNOP* and *catABC-pcaDFIJ* as well as the JAB1 *dmpBCDEFGHIKLMNOPOQ* gene clusters, each flanked by *dmpR*, *catR*, and *dmpP*, respectively, is identified here as discrete transcriptional units, indicating their independent functional roles

and pyruvate. The *dmpKLMNOP*, *catABC-pcaDFIJ*, and *dmpBCDEFGHIKLMNOPQ* operons are each flanked by a single regulatory element, *dmpR*, *catR*, and *dmpR*, respectively.

Sequence alignment results between the inferred translation products of the CEP14 and JAB1 *dmpKLMNOP* gene clusters show significant sequence similarity ($E < 1.10^{-23}$) between all subunits of the phenol monooxygenase, with a query coverage and percent identity greater than 80% and 30%, respectively (Supplementary Information Table 2). Sequence similarity between the phenol monooxygenase P3 α subunits (*dmpN*) of each strain is highly significant and the highest among all

subunits, with a query coverage and percent identity of 99% and 72%, respectively.

Operons harbouring putative genes responsible for the degradation of phenol, more specifically, the *dmp* and *cat-pca* operons in CEP14 and the *dmp* operon in JAB1, were highly upregulated in cultures grown on phenol as the sole carbon source (log₂ fold change 1.9–10.6, Table 1). Genes encoding a putative phenol monooxygenase and associated electron transfer chain (*dmpKLMNOP*) within the *dmp* operon were among the top ten upregulated transcripts between these two treatments in both strains. Additionally, peptides matching the inferred translation product of the *dmp* and *cat-pca* transcripts

Table 1 Putative genes involved in the degradation of phenol upregulated in CEP14 (JT734 locus tag prefix) and JAB1 (UYA locus tag prefix) cultures grown on phenol compared to cells grown on sodium pyruvate

Locus tag ^a	Gene abbr	Putative enzyme function	Change (log ₂ fold) ^b	Padj ^c
JT734_09015	<i>dmpP</i>	Phenol 2-monooxygenase P5 subunit	9.49	1.56E-67
JT734_09020	<i>dmpO</i>	Phenol 2-monooxygenase P4 subunit	9.62	1.39E-69
JT734_09025	<i>dmpN</i>	Phenol 2-monooxygenase P3/ α subunit	9.48	4.58E-93
JT734_09030	<i>dmpM</i>	Phenol 2-monooxygenase P2 subunit	9.61	9.17E-42
JT734_09035	<i>dmpL</i>	Phenol 2-monooxygenase P1/ β subunit	9.31	2.48E-53
JT734_09040	<i>dmpK</i>	Phenol 2-monooxygenase P0 subunit	10.56	1.68E-16
JT734_12545	<i>catB</i>	Muconate cycloisomerase	-0.06	0.93
JT734_12550	<i>catC</i>	Muconolactone D-isomerase	2.39	2.11E-08
JT734_12555	<i>catA</i>	Catechol 1,2-dioxygenase	4.07	2.04E-18
JT734_12560	<i>pcaI</i>	β -keto adipate succinyl-CoA transferase, α subunit	2.13	5.81E-07
JT734_12565	<i>pcaJ</i>	β -keto adipate succinyl-CoA transferase, β subunit	3.46	7.68E-18
JT734_12570	<i>pcaF</i>	β -keto dipyl-CoA thiolase	4.10	1.82E-27
JT734_12575	<i>pcaD</i>	β -keto adipate enol-lactone hydrolase	3.67	1.15E-28
UYA_20135	<i>dmpI</i>	2-hydroxymuconate tautomerase	2.61	1.96E-03
UYA_20140	<i>dmpH</i>	2-oxo-3-hexenedioate decarboxylase	4.53	6.78E-16
UYA_20145	<i>dmpG</i>	4-hydroxy-2-oxovalerate aldolase	3.29	6.38E-09
UYA_20150	<i>dmpF</i>	Acetaldehyde dehydrogenase	2.57	5.66E-05
UYA_20155	<i>dmpE</i>	2-keto-4-pentenoate hydratase	2.14	1.60E-03
UYA_20160	<i>dmpD</i>	2-hydroxymuconate-semialdehyde hydrolase	1.94	1.11E-02
UYA_20165	<i>dmpC</i>	2-hydroxymuconate-6-semialdehyde dehydrogenase	2.27	8.35E-05
UYA_20170	<i>dmpB</i>	Catechol 2,3-dioxygenase	2.72	6.91E-05
UYA_20175	<i>dmpQ</i>	Ferredoxin	2.15	5.24E-03
UYA_20180	<i>dmpP</i>	Phenol 2-monooxygenase P5 subunit	2.88	3.25E-05
UYA_20185	<i>dmpO</i>	Phenol 2-monooxygenase P4 subunit	2.91	1.14E-03
UYA_20190	<i>dmpN</i>	Phenol 2-monooxygenase P3/ α subunit	3.95	9.31E-06
UYA_20195	<i>dmpM</i>	Phenol 2-monooxygenase P2 subunit	4.23	1.19E-06
UYA_20200	<i>dmpL</i>	Phenol 2-monooxygenase P1/ β subunit	4.08	1.23E-06
UYA_20205	<i>dmpK</i>	Phenol 2-monooxygenase P0 subunit	2.97	3.28E-03

^a The inferred translation product of transcripts marked in bold were found in the proteome of their respective strain grown on phenol

^b Genes upregulated at with a log₂ fold change ≥ 1 in phenol-grown cells compared to sodium pyruvate-grown cells with an FDR of less than 5% (Padj < 0.05). The log₂ fold change and p-adjusted value for JT734_12545 were -0.06 and 0.93, respectively

^c Adjusted p-value (Padj) generated by the Wald test and corrected for multiple testing using the Benjamini and Hochberg method

^d All proteins identified in the proteomic analysis had $Q \leq 0.005$ (< 0.5% FDR), indicating high confidence in the assignments

were detected in the sequenced proteome of their respective strain grown on phenol (in bold, Table 1). In our heterologous *dmpKLMNOP* expression assays, we identified the accumulation of catechol, the direct product of phenol monooxygenase activity, further confirming that these genes encode a functional phenol monooxygenase (Supplementary Information Fig. 8). The gene encoding a putative muconate cycloisomerase (*catB*) was the only CDS not significantly upregulated in the CEP14 *cat-pca* operon, nor found in the proteome data of cultures grown on phenol. The reason for this selective non-expression is unclear. Possible factors include operon polarity, mRNA structure and stability, presence of repressors, or differential protein turnover, and dedicated experiments will be needed to resolve the mechanism.

Transcriptomic and proteomic screening: identification of putative *c*DCE monooxygenases

The CEP14 and JAB1 genomes were screened to identify genes that might facilitate the oxidation of *c*DCE to DCA as the initial chemical transformation during the cometabolic degradation of *c*DCE in the presence of phenol (Fig. 1). Briefly, the inferred proteome of each strain was screened using protein sequences of monooxygenases with experimentally demonstrated *c*DCE catalytic activity (Supplementary Information Table 3). The α subunit of each monooxygenase was used for proteome screening as it encodes the oxidative catalytic centre [25]. These include the α subunits of *c*DCE monooxygenase (CMOA) in *Polaromonas* sp.

JS666, butane monooxygenase (BMOA) in *Thauera butanivorans* ATCC 43655, methane monooxygenase (MMOA) in *Methylosinus trichosporium* OB3b, toluene-*o*-xylene monooxygenase (TOMOA) in *Pseudomonas stutzeri* OX1, and alkene monooxygenase (XAMOA) in *Xanthobacter autotrophicus* Py2. Initial BlastP screening results revealed that the only genes whose inferred translation products share significant sequence similarity with BMOA, MMOA, TOMOA, and XAMOA in the CEP14 and JAB1 proteomes are JT734_09025 and UYA_20190, respectively, both encoding phenol monooxygenase α subunits (*dmpN*). No CMO sequence identity matches were found in either the CEP14 or JAB1 proteome. Hierarchical clustering of monooxygenase α subunits with demonstrated *c*DCE catalytic activity based on sequence similarity revealed the grouping of these peptides into four clusters (Fig. 3, Supplementary Information Table 4). Overall, the inferred protein sequences of *bmoA*, *mmoA*, *tomoA*, JT734_09025, and UYA_20190 clustered together and shared low sequence identity with the CMO of *Polaromonas* sp. JS666.

Candidates for genes encoding a putative *c*DCE monooxygenase were identified by compiling all genes encoding putative monooxygenases that were upregulated during *c*DCE degradation, when CEP14 and JAB1 cultures were grown on phenol with *c*DCE. Both cultures completely depleted the initial amounts of phenol and *c*DCE after 12 h (CEP14) and 20 h (JAB1). Maximum degradation rates were 2.3 and 1.9 $\mu\text{mol l}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$ for phenol, and 2.9 and 5.3 $\mu\text{mol l}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$ for *c*DCE, respectively

Fig. 3 Depletion of phenol (solid blue line) and *c*DCE (dashed blue line), and accumulation of DCA (dotted blue line) in **a** CEP14 and **b** JAB1 cultures grown on 15 $\mu\text{mol l}^{-1}$ phenol and *c*DCE at 28 °C over a 12 h and 20 h time course, respectively. Data points are means \pm SD from three biological replicates. The vertical "RNA" dashed line indicates sampling time for transcriptomic analysis. Catechol was not measurable in these whole-cell assays and was only quantified in our heterologous expression experiments (Supplementary Information Fig. 8)

(Fig. 4). In comparison, the abiotic and inactivated microbial biomass controls depleted 7% and 11% of the initial amount of *c*DCE, respectively. Seven distinct monooxygenase-encoding loci were upregulated in each strain (\log_2 fold change ≥ 1 , FDR $< 5\%$; Supplementary Information Tables 5 and 6). Of these, only two loci were shared by CEP14 and JAB1: (i) JT734_09015–09040 / UYA_20180–20205, encoding the multi-component phenol monooxygenase and its electron-transfer partners (*dmpRKL MNOP*), and (ii) JT734_09880 / UYA_20305, encoding a 4-hydroxybenzoate 3-monooxygenase (*pobA*). Crucially, peptides from the *dmp* operon, but not from *pobA*, were detected in our whole-cell proteomic analyses of CEP14 and JAB1 cultures grown on phenol and *c*DCE. Consequently, we focused on *dmpKLMNOP* as the most likely *c*DCE monooxygenase, since it is the sole monooxygenase upregulated in both strains with complementary proteomic evidence.

Heterologous *dmpKLMNOP* expression: evaluating the ability of phenol monooxygenase to oxidise phenol and *c*DCE

We tested the capability of the heterologously expressed multi-component phenol monooxygenases from CEP14 and JAB1 to oxidise phenol and *c*DCE. Assays were set up using *E. coli* cultures heterologously expressing the *dmpKLMNOP* gene clusters. After 24 h of incubation, both *E. coli* cells expressing *dmpKLMNOP* gene clusters from

CEP14 and JAB1 depleted 100% of the initial amount of phenol; the accumulation of catechol, the phenol degradation product, was also observed (Supplementary Information Fig. 8). Some 50% and 30% of the initial amount of *c*DCE was depleted by *E. coli* expressing *dmpKLMNOP* from CEP14 and JAB1, respectively. Neither phenol nor *c*DCE depletion by *E. coli* cells bearing empty pQE-31 or by the autoclaved cells was observed.

Identification of *c*DCE degradation intermediates

Using whole-cell assays of CEP14 and JAB1 expressing *dmpKLMNOP*, we monitored *c*DCE depletion alongside degradative intermediate accumulation. Commercial standards were only available for DCA and 2,2-dichloroacetate. After 70 h, *c*DCE (retention time (RT) 3.344 min) decreased to 59% (CEP14) and 69% (JAB1) of initial levels (Fig. 5A). DCA (RT 5.111 min), the direct oxidation product of *c*DCE, was detectable as early as 4 h (Fig. 5A, B). A second, unidentified peak (RT 9.977 min) co-occurred with *c*DCE loss but was not characterised further (Fig. 5B, C). 2,2-dichloroacetic acid (RT 14.025 min), a subsequent hypothetical degradative intermediate arising from the dehydrogenation of DCA, was not detected in either CEP14 or JAB1 reactions at any time point monitored (data not shown). Other proposed pathway intermediates (e.g. *c*DCE epoxide, chloroglycolate, glyoxylate) were not measured in these assays, and therefore, the

Fig. 4 Heatmap of amino acid sequence similarity between the α subunit of monooxygenases with experimentally demonstrated *c*DCE catalytic activity (Supplementary Information Table 2) and the inferred translation product of genes JT734_09025 and UYA_20190 encoding putative phenol monooxygenases. Sequence similarity was calculated with the Clustal Omega multiple sequence alignment web tool. Units are in percentage, and $E < 0.05$ for all sequence similarity values. Detailed results can be found in Supplementary Information Table 2

Fig. 5 Depletion of cDCE by JAB1 and CEP14 (**A**) and detection of degradative intermediates in JAB1 (**B**) and CEP14 (**C**). **A** JAB1—dotted line, CEP14—full line; the values shown represent means from three replicates and error bars represent standard deviations. **B** and **C** Gas chromatography analyses of the JAB1 and CEP14 reactions, respectively, after 4 h of incubation; black line—the reaction with live cells, red line—the reaction with autoclaved cells. The identity of peaks was assigned based on the parallel analysis of commercial standards

proposed *c*DCE epoxide and chloroglycolate/glyoxylate pathway branches remain hypothetical.

Expression and translation of putative genes involved in *c*DCE degradation

Differential gene expression analyses identified putative genes that were upregulated during the degradation of *c*DCE in CEP14 and JAB1, suggesting their involvement in the degradation process (Fig. 1). Peptides matching the inferred translation product of these genes were also detected in the proteome of their respective strain grown on phenol in the presence of *c*DCE (bolded, Table 2). BlastP results revealed high protein sequence similarity between the inferred translation product of genes JT734_08770 and JT734_09655, two putative glutathione-independent formaldehyde dehydrogenases upregulated in CEP14, and an uncharacterised zinc-type alcohol dehydrogenase found in *Escherichia coli* strain K12 (Table 2, Supplementary Information Table 7). In addition, the glutathione-independent formaldehyde dehydrogenase encoded in gene UYA_21980 in JAB1 shares high protein sequence similarity with the glutathione-independent formaldehyde dehydrogenase of *Pseudomonas putida*, an enzyme that was shown to catalyse the NAD⁺-dependent oxidation of acetaldehydes and long-chain alcohols (Supplementary Information Table 7) [34].

Two genes encoding putative HADs (JT734_13150 and UYA_19440) were upregulated in CEP14 and JAB1 cultures grown on phenol in the presence of *c*DCE (Table 2). These enzymes are members of the prokaryotic HAD-IA family, which includes a variety of L-2 HADs that catalyse the hydrolytic dehalogenation of haloalkanoic acids, such as 2,2-dichloroacetic acid [8]. Two additional genes annotated as α/β hydrolases in CEP14 (JT734_09185 and JT734_07750) were highly upregulated (4.44- and 3.82-change fold, respectively) in the culture grown on phenol in the presence of *c*DCE. Further attempts at characterising their function did not yield conclusive results using BlastP (Supplementary Information Table 7).

Two additional transcripts annotated as α/β hydrolases in CEP14 (JT734_02575 and JT734_13910) were highly upregulated in cultures grown on phenol in the presence of *c*DCE (Table 2). The putative enzymes encoded in these genes were found to share sequence similarity with known epoxide hydrolases (Supplementary Information Table 7). Moreover, four transcripts encoding putative GSTs (JT734_00105 and JT734_08905 in CEP14, UYA_06350 and UYA_10375 in JAB1) were highly upregulated in both isolates grown on phenol and *c*DCE (Table 2). Correspondingly, genes encoding putative glutathione synthases in CEP14 and JAB1 (JT734_01885 and UYA_01900, respectively)

Table 2 Selected genes upregulated in CEP14 (JT734 locus tag prefix) and JAB1 (UYA locus tag prefix) cultures grown on phenol and *c*DCE compared to all other treatments

Locus tag ^a	Putative enzyme function	Change (log ₂ fold) ^b	Padj ^c
JT734_00105	Glutathione S-transferase	1.67	3.42E-03
JT734_01885	Glutathione synthase	1.30	1.74E-04
JT734_02575	α/β hydrolase	1.24	5.21E-02
JT734_07750	α/β hydrolase	4.18	4.16E-08
JT734_08770	Glutathione-dependent formaldehyde dehydrogenase	4.44	8.38E-24
JT734_08905	Glutathione S-transferase	1.07	6.61E-03
JT734_09185	α/β hydrolase	3.12	1.18E-14
JT734_09655	Glutathione-dependent formaldehyde dehydrogenase	3.82	9.90E-19
JT734_11180	Malate synthase	1.15	1.81E-04
JT734_13150	HAD-IA family hydrolase	2.73	9.95E-10
JT734_13910	α/β hydrolase	1.84	1.79E-08
UYA_06350	Glutathione S-transferase	1.52	6.52E-05
UYA_01900	Glutathione synthase	0.42	1.64E-02
UYA_10375	Glutathione S-transferase	2.06	2.72E-03
UYA_19440	HAD family hydrolase	1.08	1.59E-02
UYA_21980	Glutathione-independent formaldehyde dehydrogenase	2.03	2.03E-04

^a The inferred translation product of transcripts marked in bold were found in the proteome of their respective strain grown on phenol and *c*DCE

^b Genes upregulated with a log₂ fold change ≥ 1 in phenol- and *c*DCE-grown cells compared to all other treatments with an FDR of less than 5% (Padj < 0.05)

^c Adjusted *p*-value (Padj) generated by the Wald test and corrected for multiple testing using the Benjamini and Hochberg method

^d All proteins identified in the proteomic analysis had $Q \leq 0.005$ (< 0.5% FDR), indicating high confidence in the assignments

were upregulated in cultures grown on phenol in the presence of *cDCE* (Table 2).

Finally, genes of interest that are present in the genomes of CEP14 and JAB1 encode putative aconitate hydratase 1–2, isocitrate lyase, malate synthase, and citrate synthase (JT734_05435, JT734_14050, JT734_07805, JT734_11180, JT734_17475, UYA_10800, UYA_11335, UYA_13190, UYA_14460, and UYA_21840) [11, 36]. These enzymes form the complete glyoxylate pathway and hypothetically mediate the transformation of chloroglycolate/glycolate to succinate and close the proposed *cDCE* degradation pathway (Fig. 1) [15]. Only the gene encoding a putative malate synthase in CEP14 (JT734_11180) was upregulated in phenol- and *cDCE*-grown cells, linking glyoxylate formation to the TCA cycle (Table 2).

Expression and translation of putative genes involved in DNA damage, oxidative stress, and cellular acidification response mechanisms

Genes encoding putative enzymes responsible for coping with various cellular stresses were upregulated in CEP14 and JAB1 cultures grown on phenol in the presence of *cDCE* (Table 3). These enzymes included molecular chaperones, superoxide oxidases, peroxiredoxin, chloroperoxidases, universal stress proteins, and superoxide dismutases. Genes encoding putative DNA damage response-related enzymes were highly upregulated under the same treatment in CEP14. These enzymes include DEAD/DEAH box helicase, DNA-directed RNA polymerase, DNA polymerase V, and cold shock protein (Table 3). Peptides matching the inferred translation product of all genes related to oxidative stress and DNA damage responses were detected in the sequenced proteome of their respective strain grown on phenol in the presence of *cDCE* (in bold, Table 3, Supplementary Information Table 4).

Clusters of genes predicted to encode enzymes for fatty acid and acetoin metabolism (Supplementary Information Tables 8 and 9) were upregulated in CEP14 cultures, but not in JAB1 cultures, when grown on phenol and *cDCE*. Both acetoin synthesis, a pH-neutral process, and the alteration of membrane fatty acid composition, shifting from unsaturated to saturated species, have been shown to buffer intracellular acidification [18, 49]. In parallel, genes within the *pca-qui* operon, particularly *pcaC* (JT734_12740) encoding a putative 4-carboxymuconolactone decarboxylase, were strongly upregulated under these conditions in CEP14, a pattern previously linked to oxidative stress resistance via aromatic antioxidant production and membrane maintenance [26, 46] (Supplementary Information Table 10). We speculate that these gene clusters are part of a pathway that helps mitigate

Table 3 Putative genes involved in cellular oxidative stress and DNA damage response upregulated in CEP14 (JT734 locus tag prefix) and JAB1 (UYA locus tag prefix) cultures grown on phenol and *cDCE* compared to all other treatments

Locus tag ^a	Putative enzyme function	Change (log ₂ fold) ^b	Padj ^c
JT734_00675	DEAD/DEAH box helicase	3.09	4.40E-10
JT734_01025	DNA-directed RNA polymerase subunit omega	3.61	3.13E-05
JT734_04225	Molecular chaperone HtpG	1.18	1.77E-06
JT734_08495	Superoxide oxidase	2.43	5.32E-08
JT734_08950	Peroxiredoxin	1.23	1.34E-02
JT734_08780	DNA polymerase V	4.37	2.20E-13
JT734_08785	DNA polymerase V	4.93	3.05E-23
JT734_12450	Chloroperoxidase	2.02	7.87E-07
JT734_13465	DNA polymerase V	5.09	9.13E-18
JT734_13695	DNA breaking-rejoining protein	2.96	1.18E-25
JT734_14750	Cold shock protein	3.29	1.65E-06
JT734_15030	DNA polymerase V	4.31	4.91E-28
JT734_18460	Peroxiredoxin	1.70	9.13E-08
UYA_06275	Peroxiredoxin	3.66	2.85E-04
UYA_10080	Molecular chaperone IbpA	2.18	8.07E-03
UYA_16930	Universal stress protein UspA	1.24	8.26E-03
UYA_17460	Superoxide dismutase	1.82	4.46E-03
UYA_18885	Molecular chaperone DnaK	1.78	3.90E-06
UYA_18950	ATP-dependent chaperone ClpB	1.36	1.84E-04

^a The inferred translation product of transcripts marked in bold were found in the proteome of their respective strain grown on phenol and *cDCE*

^b Genes upregulated with a log₂ fold change ≥ 1 in phenol- and *cDCE*-grown cells compared to all other treatments with an FDR of less than 5% (Padj < 0.05)

^c Adjusted *p*-value (Padj) generated by the Wald test and corrected for multiple testing using the Benjamini and Hochberg method

^d All proteins identified in the proteomic analysis had $Q \leq 0.005$ (< 0.5% FDR), indicating high confidence in the assignments

oxidative and acid stress arising from the accumulation of DCA, a reactive intermediate in *cDCE* cometabolic degradation in CEP14. Consistent with this unique induction, cultures of CEP14 accumulated significantly more DCA than JAB1 (Fig. 4), implicating greater stress during *cDCE* cometabolism. However, defining the precise molecular mechanisms underlying this response is beyond the scope of this study.

Discussion

Cometabolism plays a crucial role in the degradation of many environmental pollutants, as the presence of a primary substrate can stimulate the degradation of structurally similar contaminants [17]. In this study, we demonstrate that phenol is a suitable primary substrate to stimulate the degradation of *cDCE* and that phenol monooxygenase is responsible for initiating the aerobic

cometabolic degradation of *c*DCE in CEP14 and JAB1. While RNA-seq fold changes were subjected to rigorous quality controls, we acknowledge that relying solely on RNA-seq can be influenced by technical biases including normalisation and mapping artefacts. Importantly, the mRNA fold changes reported here are strongly corroborated by our proteomics data, providing independent support for the key transcriptional trends. Indeed, genes within the *dmp* operon are among the most upregulated genes and are translated in CEP14 and JAB1 cultures grown on phenol in the presence of *c*DCE. Our transcriptomic and proteomic screening identified phenol monooxygenase (encoded in the *dmpKLMNOP* gene cluster) as the only putative *c*DCE monooxygenase in both strains. The *dmpKLMNOP* clusters are highly conserved, underscoring their functional homology and evolutionary relatedness (Fig. 2, Supplementary Information Table 2) [20, 50]. Despite this conservation, protein sequence comparisons revealed only limited similarity to known monooxygenases with known *c*DCE-oxidising activity, suggesting that a broader diversity of monooxygenase enzymes may be capable of cometabolic *c*DCE oxidation than previously appreciated. The observed depletion of phenol and *c*DCE and the accumulation of DCA in *E. coli* cultures heterologously expressing the *dmpKLMNOP* gene cluster from each strain confirms that the phenol monooxygenases of CEP14 and JAB1 oxidise *c*DCE to DCA in the presence of phenol.

The detection of DCA in CEP14 and JAB1 cultures during *c*DCE degradation suggests that the pathway proceeds through the intermediate DCA (Fig. 5B, C), which could be converted to 2,2-dichloroacetic acid and then to chloroglycolate (Fig. 1). However, no epoxide intermediate was detected, and alternate enzymatic or non-enzymatic routes to DCA cannot be excluded in the absence of direct evidence for the epoxide branch. Genes encoding three uncharacterised putative aldehyde dehydrogenases (JT734_08770, JT734_09655, and UYA_21980) were upregulated and translated in CEP14 and JAB1 cultures during *c*DCE degradation and DCA accumulation (Table 2, Supplementary Information Table 7). Although initial functional annotation indicates formaldehyde as a substrate for these enzymes, further investigation suggests they may transform alternative substrates, including long-chain alcohols and acetaldehydes (Supplementary Information Table 7). We hypothesise that these genes encode enzymes responsible for dehydrogenating DCA to 2,2-dichloroacetic acid, the primary and secondary intermediates, respectively, in our proposed *c*DCE degradation pathway in CEP14 and JAB1 (Fig. 1).

While 2,2-dichloroacetic acid was not detected, genes encoding HADs and α/β hydrolases (JT734_13150, JT734_08770, and JT734_09655 in CEP14, UYA_19440

in JAB1) were highly upregulated and expressed in CEP14 and JAB1 cultures grown on phenol and in which *c*DCE depletion was observed (Table 2). The absence of 2,2-dichloroacetic acid in our analyses could be due to its high reactivity and instability, particularly in the presence of microbial biomass. We further hypothesise that JT734_13150, JT734_08770, JT734_09655, and UYA_19440 encode dichloroacetic acid dehalogenases that mediate the transformation of 2,2-dichloroacetic acid to chloroglycolate, the secondary and tertiary degradative intermediates in the proposed CEP14 and JAB1 *c*DCE degradation pathway (Fig. 1). The dechlorination of chloroglycolate to glyoxal is predicted to occur spontaneously and the latter can be fed in the glyoxylate and TCA cycles.

Transcripts encoding putative enzymes involved in the detoxification of reactive compounds, namely, epoxide hydrolases (JT734_02575 and JT734_13910 in CEP14) and GSTs (JT734_00105 and JT734_08905 in CEP14, UYA_06350 and UYA_10375 in JAB1), were upregulated and translated in CEP14 and JAB1 cultures during *c*DCE degradation (Table 2, Supplementary Information Table 7). The activity of certain epoxide hydrolases and GSTs towards halogenated epoxides, including *c*DCE epoxide, has been demonstrated experimentally in various studies [2]. Their activity can enhance the aerobic monooxygenase-mediated mineralisation of *c*DCE by mediating the detoxification of cellular epoxides [2]. The activity of GSTs, which leads to the formation of glutathione-epoxide adducts that are more readily degradable, is further supported in CEP14 and JAB1 by the observed upregulation of transcripts encoding putative glutathione synthases (JT734_01885 in CEP14 and UYA_01900 in JAB1). Although the formation of *c*DCE epoxide as an intermediate was not directly detected, we hypothesise that these genes contribute to its degradation as well as the breakdown of other reactive compounds generated as byproducts in the proposed *c*DCE degradative pathway (Fig. 1).

The upregulation of genes involved in antioxidant defence mechanisms in CEP14 and JAB1 suggests that ROS form during the cometabolic degradation of *c*DCE, leading to cellular oxidative stress (Table 3). In CEP14, the expression of genes related to oxidative stress response was accompanied by an upregulation and translation of genes involved in DNA repair mechanisms (Table 3). The excessive formation of ROS, such as *c*DCE epoxides, can cause cellular damage by forming adducts with macromolecules such as DNA [45]. These results are consistent with our findings that the cometabolic degradation of *c*DCE is initiated by a monooxygenase which belongs to a group of enzymes that can activate molecules through epoxidation, leading to the formation

of ROS [30]. Interestingly, no transcripts involved in DNA repair mechanisms were upregulated in JAB1 (Table 3). This may indicate that JAB1 is more efficient at coping with ROS intermediates, preventing cellular DNA damage.

Finally, a total of 112 (18.30%) and 39 (15.35%) of the transcripts upregulated in response to growth on phenol in the presence of *c*DCE in CEP14 and JAB1, respectively, are of unknown function, limiting our ability to speculate on their role in the degradation of *c*DCE. The transcriptional response of JAB1 cultures to growth on phenol in the presence of *c*DCE was lesser than that of CEP14, with ~60% fewer genes being significantly upregulated. These results may be attributed to the environment from which JAB1 was isolated—an industrial legacy-contaminated site with multiple contaminants, including PCBs [36]. As such, JAB1 may be better adapted to degrade environmental pollutants, including aromatic and genotoxic chlorinated compounds such as PCBs and *c*DCE, and to mitigate cellular oxidative stress.

Our findings are consistent with prior studies, which show that phenol can serve as a growth substrate to stimulate the cometabolic degradation of *c*DCE and related compounds [9, 17]. For instance, Fraraccio et al. [17] demonstrated enhanced *c*DCE degradation in response to phenolic plant secondary metabolites, supporting the notion that monoaromatic compounds can broadly induce *c*DCE-oxidising enzymes. However, unlike *Polaromonas* sp. JS666, where a distinct *c*DCE monooxygenase has been characterised [19, 33], our data show that CEP14 and JAB1 rely on phenol monooxygenases that are not evolutionarily or structurally aligned with the canonical *c*DCE-degrading enzyme. This divergence highlights a potentially underrecognised route for *c*DCE degradation via phenol-inducible oxygenases, which may be more prevalent in mixed-contaminant sites co-polluted with monoaromatics. Furthermore, our identification of stress-related gene expression (e.g. DNA repair in CEP14) adds a dimension often missing in previous studies, which have not explored the oxidative or genotoxic responses in cometabolically active strains.

The identification of phenol monooxygenase as the initiating enzyme for *c*DCE degradation in CEP14 and JAB1 provides a foundation for applied strategies in bioremediation. These strains, or their phenol-inducible monooxygenase systems, could be harnessed for the aerobic treatment of *c*DCE in environments co-contaminated with monoaromatic compounds such as phenol, which are frequently encountered at petrochemical and legacy industrial sites [1, 27]. Our findings also underscore the enzymatic diversity of monooxygenases capable of cometabolic *c*DCE oxidation, highlighting that structurally distinct enzymes beyond the well-characterised

*c*DCE monooxygenases may play key roles in biotransformation at mixed-contaminant sites. Moreover, the upregulation of stress response and DNA repair genes in CEP14 suggests an intrinsic capacity to tolerate oxidative or genotoxic byproducts generated during cometabolism, a feature that may enhance robustness under environmental conditions. These traits make CEP14 and JAB1 promising candidates for bioaugmentation, particularly in engineered systems targeting complex contaminant mixtures.

Conclusion

This study provides direct molecular evidence that phenol monooxygenase initiates the cometabolic degradation of *c*DCE in *Acinetobacter pittii* CEP14 and *Ectopseudomonas alcaliphila* JAB1, expanding the diversity of known enzymatic systems involved in aerobic *c*DCE degradation. By linking gene expression, protein detection, and functional activity, this study bridges a critical gap between environmental genomics and applied bioremediation. As such, it contributes both mechanistic insight and a platform for translational applications in contaminated site management. These findings deepen our understanding of phenol-driven cometabolism in mixed-contaminant environments and clarify the enzymatic basis for prior observations of *c*DCE degradation in the presence of monoaromatics. These insights contribute to a broader understanding of microbial metabolism in chemically complex environments and may inform the development of bioaugmentation strategies for mixed-contaminant plumes. Future work should prioritise (i) elucidating the complete enzymatic steps in the proposed two-branch degradation pathway, (ii) quantifying degradation kinetics under environmentally relevant conditions, and (iii) evaluating the efficacy of these strains or their enzymes in pilot-scale or field-scale remediation systems. Together, these directions will help translate fundamental mechanistic knowledge into practical tools for environmental bioremediation.

Supplementary Information

The online version contains supplementary material available at <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12302-025-01237-z>.

Supplementary material 1.

Acknowledgements

The authors wish to thank two anonymous reviewers for their comments, which helped shape the final version of the manuscript.

Author contributions

SF, JS, MS, and OU designed the study. JS, KAD, AS, and OU provided funding. OU, MS, and JS supervised the project. ID and AS collected the samples. SF, JR, JS, APP, LMG, and MH carried out the experiments. MD, SF, APP, MS, and JS

analysed the data. MD, SF, JS, APP, KAD, LMG, MS, and OU contributed to the interpretation of the results. MD wrote the manuscript with support from JS, MS, and OU. All authors approved the final version of the manuscript.

Funding

This work was funded by a grant from the Czech Science Foundation (project no. 22-00150S); by a grant from the Programme Johannes Amos Comenius under the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic (project number CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004597); and by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme (GA 101060625). Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union can be held responsible for them. Computational resources were provided by the e-INFRA CZ project (ID:90254), supported by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic. The funders had no role in study design, data collection and interpretation, or the decision to submit the work for publication.

Data availability

The datasets generated during and/or analysed during the current study are available in GenBank under accession numbers CP016162.1 (*Ectopseudomonas alcaliphila* JAB1; BioProject accession number PRJNA104953) and CP084921.1-CP084924.1 (*Acinetobacter pittii* CEP14; BioProject accession number PRJNA770122), and the SRA under accession numbers SRX26459013-SRX26459032 (BioProject accession number PRJNA1176194).

Declarations

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Not applicable.

Consent for publication

Not applicable.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Author details

¹Faculty of Food and Biochemical Technology, Department of Biochemistry and Microbiology, University of Chemistry and Technology, Prague, Prague, Czech Republic. ²Department of Genomics and Bioinformatics, Institute of Molecular Genetics of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Prague, Czech Republic. ³Centre for BioNano Interactions, University College Dublin, Dublin, Ireland. ⁴Institute for Nanomaterials, Advanced Technologies and Innovation, Faculty of Science, Humanities and Education, Technical University of Liberec, Liberec, Czech Republic. ⁵Department of Genetics and Molecular Diagnostics, Regional Hospital Liberec, Liberec, Czech Republic. ⁶Faculty of Environmental Technology, Department of Environmental Chemistry, University of Chemistry and Technology, Prague, Prague, Czech Republic. ⁷Present Address: Scripps Institution of Oceanography, University of California San Diego, San Diego, USA. ⁸Present Address: Centro Singular de Investigación en Química Biolóxica e Materiais Moleculares (CIQUS), Universidade de Santiago de Compostela, Santiago de Compostela, Spain.

Received: 28 March 2025 Accepted: 6 October 2025

Published online: 07 November 2025

References

- Ahmaruzzaman Md, Mishra SR, Gadore V, Yadav G, Roy S, Bhattacharjee B, Bhuyan A, Hazarika B, Darabdhara J, Kumari K (2024) Phenolic compounds in water: from toxicity and source to sustainable solutions – an integrated review of removal methods, advanced technologies, cost analysis, and future prospects. *J Environ Chem Eng* 12:112964. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2024.112964>
- Allocati N, Federici L, Masulli M, Di Ilio C (2009) Glutathione transferases in bacteria. *FEBS J* 276:58–75. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1742-4658.2008.06743.x>
- Andrews S (2010) FastQC: A Quality Control Tool for High Throughput Sequence Data [WWW Document]. <https://qubeshub.org/resources/fastqc>
- Aramaki T, Blanc-Mathieu R, Endo H, Ohkubo K, Kanehisa M, Goto S, Ogata H (2020) Kofamkoala: KEGG ortholog assignment based on profile HMM and adaptive score threshold. *Bioinformatics* 36:2251–2252. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/bt2859>
- Bolger AM, Lohse M, Usadel B (2014) Trimmomatic: a flexible trimmer for Illumina sequence data. *Bioinformatics* 30:2114–2120. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btu170>
- Boutet E, Lieberherr D, Tognolli M, Schneider M, Bansal P, Bridge AJ, Poux S, Bougueleret L, Xenarios I (2016) UniProtKB/Swiss-Prot, the manually annotated section of the UniProt KnowledgeBase: how to use the entry view. In: Edwards D (ed) *Plant bioinformatics, methods in molecular biology*. Springer, New York, pp 23–54
- Broholm K, Ludvigsen L, Jensen TF, Østergaard H (2005) Aerobic biodegradation of vinyl chloride and cis-1,2-dichloroethylene in aquifer sediments. *Chemosphere* 60:1555–1564. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2005.02.056>
- Burroughs AM, Allen KN, Dunaway-Mariano D, Aravind L (2006) Evolutionary genomics of the HAD superfamily: understanding the structural adaptations and catalytic diversity in a superfamily of phosphoesterases and allied enzymes. *J Mol Biol* 361:1003–1034. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmb.2006.06.049>
- Chang Y-C, Venkateswar Reddy M, Choi D (2021) Cometabolic degradation of toxic trichloroethene or cis-1,2-dichloroethene with phenol and production of poly-β-hydroxybutyrate (PHB). *Green Chem* 23:2729–2737. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D1GC00265A>
- Coleman NV, Mattes TE, Gossett JM, Spain JC (2002) Biodegradation of cis-dichloroethene as the sole carbon source by a β-proteobacterium. *Appl Environ Microbiol* 68:2726–2730. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.68.6.2726-2730.2002>
- Desmarais M, Fraraccio S, Dolinova I, Ridl J, Strnad H, Kubatova H, Sevcu A, Suman J, Strejcek M, Uhlik O (2022) Genomic analysis of *Acinetobacter pittii* CEP14 reveals its extensive biodegradation capabilities, including cometabolic degradation of cis-1,2-dichloroethene. *Antonie Van Leeuwenhoek* 115:1041–1057. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10482-022-01752-6>
- Doherty RE (2000) A history of the production and use of carbon tetrachloride, tetrachloroethylene, trichloroethylene and 1,1,1-trichloroethane in the United States: part 1—historical background; carbon tetrachloride and tetrachloroethylene. *Environ Forensics* 1:69–81. <https://doi.org/10.1006/enfo.2000.0010>
- Dolinová I, Štrojsová M, Černík M, Němeček J, Macháčková J, Ševců A (2017) Microbial degradation of chloroethenes: a review. *Environ Sci Pollut Res* 24:13262–13283. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-017-8867-y>
- Doughty DM, Sayavedra-Soto LA, Arp DJ, Bottomley PJ (2005) Effects of dichloroethene isomers on the induction and activity of butane monooxygenase in the alkane-oxidizing bacterium *Pseudomonas butanovora*. *Appl Environ Microbiol* 71:6054–6059. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.71.10.6054-6059.2005>
- Ensign SA (2006) Revisiting the glyoxylate cycle: alternate pathways for microbial acetate assimilation. *Mol Microbiol* 61:274–276. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2958.2006.05247.x>
- Ensign SA, Hyman MR, Arp DJ (1992) Cometabolic degradation of chlorinated alkenes by alkene monooxygenase in a propylene-grown *Xanthobacter* strain. *Appl Environ Microbiol* 58:3038–3046. <https://doi.org/10.1128/aem.58.9.3038-3046.1992>
- Fraraccio S, Strejcek M, Dolinova I, Macek T, Uhlik O (2017) Secondary compound hypothesis revisited: selected plant secondary metabolites promote bacterial degradation of cis-1,2-dichloroethylene (cDCE). *Sci Rep* 7:8406. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-07760-1>
- Guan N, Liu L (2020) Microbial response to acid stress: mechanisms and applications. *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol* 104:51–65. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00253-019-10226-1>
- Jennings LK, Chartrand MMG, Lacrampe-Couloume G, Lollar BS, Spain JC, Gossett JM (2009) Proteomic and transcriptomic analyses reveal genes upregulated by cis-dichloroethene in *Polaromonas* sp. strain JS666. *Appl Environ Microbiol* 75:3733–3744. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.00031-09>
- Jõesaar M, Viggor S, Heinari E, Naanuri E, Mehike M, Leito I, Heinari A (2017) Strategy of *Pseudomonas pseudoalcaligenes* C70 for effective

- degradation of phenol and salicylate. *PLoS ONE* 12:e0173180. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0173180>
21. Jones P, Binns D, Chang H-Y, Fraser M, Li W, McAnulla C, McWilliam H, Maslen J, Mitchell A, Nuka G, Pesseat S, Quinn AF, Sangrador-Vegas A, Scheremetjew M, Yong S-Y, Lopez R, Hunter S (2014) Interproscan 5: genome-scale protein function classification. *Bioinformatics* 30:1236–1240. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btu031>
 22. Jugder B-E, Ertan H, Lee M, Manefield M, Marquis CP (2015) Reductive dehalogenases come of age in biological destruction of organohalides. *Trends Biotechnol* 33:595–610. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tibtech.2015.07.004>
 23. Kanehisa M (2000) KEGG: Kyoto encyclopedia of genes and genomes. *Nucleic Acids Res* 28:27–30. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/28.1.27>
 24. Kopylova E, Noé L, Touzet H (2012) SortMeRNA: fast and accurate filtering of ribosomal RNAs in metatranscriptomic data. *Bioinformatics* 28:3211–3217. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/bts611>
 25. Leahy JG, Batchelor PJ, Morcomb SM (2003) Evolution of the soluble diiron monooxygenases. *FEMS Microbiol Rev* 27:449–479. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-6445\(03\)00023-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-6445(03)00023-8)
 26. Lee J-Y, Lee HJ, Seo J, Kim E-S, Lee H-S, Kim P (2014) Artificial oxidative stress-tolerant *Corynebacterium glutamicum*. *AMB Express* 4(1):15. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13568-014-0015-1>
 27. Li H, Zhang S, Wang X, Yang J, Gu J, Zhu R, Wang P, Lin K, Liu Y (2015) Aerobic biodegradation of trichloroethylene and phenol co-contaminants in groundwater by a bacterial community using hydrogen peroxide as the sole oxygen source. *Environ Technol* 36:667–674. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09593330.2014.957730>
 28. Lopez-Echartea E, Suman J, Smrhova T, Ridl J, Pajer P, Strejcek M, Uhlík O (2021) Genomic analysis of dibenzofuran-degrading *Pseudomonas veronii* strain Pvy reveals its biodegradative versatility. *G3 Genes|Genomes|Genetics* 11:jkaa030. <https://doi.org/10.1093/g3journal/jkaa030>
 29. Love M, Anders S, Huber W (2014) Differential analysis of count data—the DESeq2 package. *Genome Biol* 15:10–1186
 30. Mattes TE, Alexander AK, Coleman NV (2010) Aerobic biodegradation of the chloroethenes: pathways, enzymes, ecology, and evolution. *FEMS Microbiol Rev* 34:445–475. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1574-6976.2010.00210.x>
 31. McGachy L, Skarohlid R, Martinec M, Roskova Z, Smrhova T, Strejcek M, Uhlík O, Marek J (2021) Effect of chelated iron activated peroxydisulfate oxidation on perchloroethene-degrading microbial consortium. *Chemosphere* 266:128928. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2020.128928>
 32. Moran MJ, Zogorski JS, Squillace PJ (2007) Chlorinated solvents in groundwater of the United States. *Environ Sci Technol* 41:74–81. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es061553y>
 33. Nishino SF, Shin KA, Gossett JM, Spain JC (2013) Cytochrome P450 initiates degradation of *cis*-dichloroethene by *Polaromonas* sp. strain JS666. *Appl Environ Microbiol* 79:2263–2272. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.03445-12>
 34. Oppenheimer NJ, Henahan GTM, Huete-Pérez JA, Ito K (1996) *P. putida* formaldehyde dehydrogenase. In: Weiner H, Lindahl R, Crabb DW, Flynn TG (eds) *Enzymology and molecular biology of carbonyl metabolism 6*, advances in experimental medicine and biology. Springer, Boston, pp 417–423
 35. Patro R, Duggal G, Love MI, Izrarry RA, Kingsford C (2017) Salmon provides fast and bias-aware quantification of transcript expression. *Nat Methods* 14:417–419. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmeth.4197>
 36. Ridl J, Suman J, Fraraccio S, Hradilova M, Strejcek M, Cajthaml T, Zubrova A, Macek T, Strnad H, Uhlík O (2018) Complete genome sequence of *Pseudomonas alcaliphila* JAB1 (=DSM 26533), a versatile degrader of organic pollutants. *Stand Genomic Sci* 13:3. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40793-017-0306-7>
 37. Rudra B, Gupta RS (2024) Phylogenomics studies and molecular markers reliably demarcate genus *Pseudomonas* sensu stricto and twelve other Pseudomonadaceae species clades representing novel and emended genera. *Front Microbiol* 14:1273665. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2023.1273665>
 38. Shim H, Ryoo D, Barbieri P, Wood TK (2001) Aerobic degradation of mixtures of tetrachloroethylene, trichloroethylene, dichloroethylenes, and vinyl chloride by toluene-*o*-xylene monooxygenase of *Pseudomonas stutzeri* OX1. *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol* 56:265–269. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s002530100650>
 39. Sievers F, Higgins DG (2014) Clustal omega, accurate alignment of very large numbers of sequences. In: Russell DJ (ed) *Multiple sequence alignment methods, methods in molecular biology*. Humana Press, Totowa, pp 105–116
 40. Suman J, Sredlova K, Fraraccio S, Jerabkova M, Strejcek M, Kabickova H, Cajthaml T, Uhlík O (2024) Transformation of hydroxylated polychlorinated biphenyls by bacterial 2-hydroxybiphenyl 3-monoxygenase. *Chemosphere* 349:140909. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2023.140909>
 41. Suman J, Strejcek M, Zubrova A, Capek J, Wald J, Michalikova K, Hradilova M, Sredlova K, Semerad J, Cajthaml T, Uhlík O (2021) Predominant biphenyl dioxygenase from legacy polychlorinated biphenyl (PCB)-contaminated soil is a part of unusual gene cluster and transforms flavone and flavanone. *Front Microbiol* 12:644708. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2021.644708>
 42. Tatusova T, DiCuccio M, Badretdin A, Chetverin V, Nawrocki EP, Zaslavsky L, Lomsadze A, Pruitt KD, Borodovsky M, Ostell J (2016) NCBI prokaryotic genome annotation pipeline. *Nucleic Acids Res* 44:6614–6624. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkw569>
 43. Tsien HC, Brusseau GA, Hanson RS, Waclett LP (1989) Biodegradation of trichloroethylene by *Methylosinus trichosporium* OB3b. *Appl Environ Microbiol* 55:3155–3161. <https://doi.org/10.1128/aem.55.12.3155-3161.1989>
 44. Tyanova S, Temu T, Cox J (2016) The maxquant computational platform for mass spectrometry-based shotgun proteomics. *Nat Protoc* 11:2301–2319. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nprot.2016.136>
 45. Van Hylckama Vlieg JE, Poelarends GJ, Mars AE, Janssen D (2000) Detoxification of reactive intermediates during microbial metabolism of halogenated compounds. *Curr Opin Microbiol* 3:257–262. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1369-5274\(00\)00086-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1369-5274(00)00086-2)
 46. Wang G, Hong Y, Johnson MK, Maier RJ (2006) Lipid peroxidation as a source of oxidative damage in *Helicobacter pylori*: protective roles of peroxiredoxins. *Biochim Biophys Acta* 1760(11):1596–1603. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbagen.2006.05.005>
 47. Willmann A, Tiehm A (2024) Aerobic co-metabolic *cis*-Dichloroethene degradation with Trichloroethene as primary substrate and effects of concentration ratios. *Chemosphere* 350:141000. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2023.141000>
 48. Organization WH, Organization WH (eds) (2002) *Guidelines for drinking-water quality. Addendum, microbiological agents in drinking water*, 2nd edn. World Health Organization, Geneva
 49. Xiao Z, Xu P (2007) Acetoin metabolism in bacteria. *Crit Rev Microbiol* 33:127–140. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408410701364604>
 50. Xu Y, Chen M, Zhang W, Lin M (2003) Genetic organization of genes encoding phenol hydroxylase, benzoate 1,2-dioxygenase alpha subunit and its regulatory proteins in *Acinetobacter calcoaceticus* PHEA-2. *Curr Microbiol* 46:235–240. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00284-002-3840-4>
 51. Zalesak M, Ruzicka J, Vicha R, Dvorackova M (2017) Cometabolic degradation of dichloroethenes by *Comamonas testosteroni* RF2. *Chemosphere* 186:919–927. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2017.07.156>

Publisher's Note

Springer Nature remains neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.